

Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas

also known as "Maga Brāhmaṇas"

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Entry tags: Syncretic Religions, Indo-Iranian Religions, Hinduism, Religious Group

The Śākadvīpiya (or Maga) Brāhmaṇas are a little known Brahmanical group mainly settled in Rājasthān and Bihār. According to the ancient texts, they are Hindu Sun worshippers but also include Buddhist, Jaina and Iranian features in their cult. In the Sām̐ba- and Bhaviṣya-purāṇa, the story of their legendary migration is told: Sām̐ba, Kṛṣṇa's son, is hit by leprosy, and only the Sun god can heal him. For this reason, the Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas, experts in Sun cult, are called from Iran to Northern India to worship the god and heal Sām̐ba's sickness. Very interestingly, many Iranian elements are present both in the content and in the language of these Purāṇic passages, such as Iranian loanwords, ritual objects and customs. Over the centuries, the Śākadvīpiya presence is registered in India in epigraphic sources, in the peculiar Sun god iconography with Iranian traits, by the astrologer and astronomer Varāhamihira (6th century CE), travellers', and three late poems, namely the Magavyakti, the Sām̐vavijaya and the Khalavaktracapeṭika (probably ca. 16th century), which record the family names and further legends on the Śākadvīpiyas. They must have been very famous in northern courts in some periods, especially in relation to Sun worship, and even the fact that their texts have been inserted in the Purāṇic literature testifies to their social importance; the same is valid for the later poems. Their cult is perfectly inserted in the syncretistic tendency that has characterized North Indian cults since the first centuries CE, when some groups living in the lands in between Iran and India moved to North India and established powerful reigns there. The Śākadvīpiyas may have followed the same route, settled in India, built their sacred places, and specialised in Sun cult. Nowadays, Śākadvīpiya communities are still present on Indian soil, in the same ancient areas of settlement. Śākadvīpiya priests are still versed in astrology and the main solar festivals are still celebrated by the community. Unfortunately, the new generations are generally not interested in their peculiar customs, and most of them are aware of belonging to a specific tradition only because of marriage endogamic policies. However, in the last years, small groups of Śākadvīpiya people have started again cultivating the interest in their traditions and rediscovered their ancient customs. To revitalise the community, new associations have been created and some magazines, like the Rājasthāni Brahmāṇḍ Cetnā, have been published on monthly basis.

Date Range: 2 CE - 21 CE

Region: North India (Rājasthān and Bihār)

Region tags: India

Settlement areas of the Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas since ancient times to the present.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Srivastava, V.C. 2013. Sām̐ba-Purāṇa (An Exhaustive Introduction, Sanskrit Text, English Translation, Notes & Index of Verses), Parimal Publications: Delhi.
- Source 2: The Śākadvīpiya magazine 'Brahmāṇḍ Cetnā'.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.shakdwipi.com/community/>
- Source 1 Description: A Śākadvīpiya website. They are particularly active online for marriage arrangements.
- Source 2 URL: <https://vibhanshu.wordpress.com/2011/03/31/history-of-sakaldwipiya-brahmins-or-bhojaka-brahmins/>
- Source 2 Description: A blog on Śākadvīpiya history.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: https://archive.org/details/Upapurana/11.samba_purana/page/n1/mode/2up?view=theater
- Source 1 Description: An edition of the Sām̐ba-purāṇa in Sanskrit preserved online in the repository Goblethics.net.
- Source 2 URL: https://archive.org/details/Bhavishya_Mahapurana_Sanskrit_-_Venkateswara_Press_1917/BhavishyaMahapuranaSanskritPart1/page/n21/mode/2up
- Source 2 Description: An edition of the Bhaviṣya-purāṇa in Sanskrit published by the Venkateswara Press in Mumbai.
- Source 3 URL: <http://orient-digital.staatsbibliothek-berlin.de/servlets/solr/select?q=%2BobjectType%3A%22islamhs%22+%2B%28%28%2BallMeta%3AMs.%2BallMeta%3Aor.%2BallMeta%3Aoc.%2BallMeta%3A48%29+%28%2>
- Source 3 Description: The digitised copy of a manuscript preserved in Berlin at the Staatsbibliothek containing Sām̐vavijaya, Khalavaktracapeṭika and Magavyakti texts.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

— Yes

Notes: The Śākadvīpiyas live in the Indian society, which is probably one of the most pluralistic from a religious point of view. They are constantly in touch with other cultural and religious communities.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

— Yes

Notes: Historical religious cults have always been in competition for the prestige in society and at court. Brahmins have never been particularly affected by the competition as they have been generally held in high esteem among the Indian society. The Śākadvīpiyas are not always recognised by other Brahmins as belonging to the Brāhmaṇa caste, as they claim to have come from Iranian lands.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

— No

Notes: Traditionally, Hinduism and the Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas are not accommodating with other cultures, and think to be superior not only to the other religious groups, but also to the other Hindu castes. However, in the last years, pan-religious trend, in which the pantheon is composed by divinities belonging to different traditions, have become popular even among the Śākadvīpiyas.

Reference: Martina Palladino. *The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present* (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

— No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

— No

Notes: The sadly famous conflict between Hindus and Muslims, which has lasted over centuries and has been characterized by some violent episodes, does not involve the Śākadvīpiya group.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

— No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

— No

Notes: The affiliation is only granted by birth.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

— No

Does the religion have official political support

— No

Notes: The Śākadvīpiyas have no direct representation or support in the political sphere, but there are some members of the Parliament who are Śākadvīpiyas.

Reference: Martina Palladino. *The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present* (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.215 sqq.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

— No

Notes: Even if the concept of apostasy is not accepted or applicable to this religious group, many Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas are no longer aware of their tradition and sympathize for new pan-religious trends.

Reference: Martina Palladino. *The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present* (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.189

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 100000

Notes: A census of the community is unfortunately not available. According to some members of the community, the total number of Śākadvipīyas in Rājasthān would be around one hundred thousand.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvipīya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.162

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.1

Notes: In Rājasthān, with a population estimated to be of more than 82 million people, the Śākadvipīya Brāhmaṇas represent a real minority. According to some members, in Jodhpur, Rājasthān, they represent the 8% of the total population. This figure is probably higher than the real one, but Rājasthān is certainly the state in which the Śākadvipīya population is mainly gathered.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvipīya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.162

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Different people are in charge of different tasks and responsibilities, but there is no official recognition of leaders in the community. Paṇḍits and priests are highly respected from a religious and social point of view.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Like all the other Hindus, the Śākadvipīya Brāhmaṇas rely on the Vedas as their primary source. According to the members of the community, the Śākadvipīyas anciently had an additional Veda, which was then destroyed. In the Bhaviṣya-purāṇa (1, 140, 36-37), some 'reversed' Vedas are mentioned, which had been proclaimed by Brahmā in ancient times like the other Vedas.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvipīya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.166 sqq.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Sāmba- and Bhaviṣya-purāṇas are certainly important written texts for the Śākadvipīyas. The community also have the memory of a Saura-purāṇa in ancient time, which has probably to be identified with 'the book of the Magas' mentioned by the philosopher Bhāvaviveka (6th century CE).

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvipīya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.166

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Prayers to the Sun god (like the Gāyatrī mantra) and rituals are very important. The Śākadvipīya priests are versed in the recitation of the Vedas and on ritual activities. Moreover, some legends about the Śākadvipīyas' migration are transmitted orally among the different communities.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvipīya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: Not all the texts belonging to the Śākadvipīya tradition are alterable. Purāṇic texts, as a genre, underwent many modifications over the centuries and many layers have been

gradually added. Especially the Bhaviṣya-purāṇa is a late composite text, and many additions have occurred over the centuries.

Reference: R.C. Hazra. Saura and Vaiṣṇava Upapurāṇas. Calcutta: Sanskrit College.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Vedic texts are now codified, but they are still transmitted orally by the priests, specialists of rituals. They undergo a long training and learn the sacred texts by heart.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Vedas represent for sure a codified canon for all the Hindus.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Nowadays, the Śākadvīpiya temples are generally of modest size, and Śākadvīpiya priests take care of them. In Rājasthān, the Sūrya Mandir in Rāṇakpur (15th century), near Udaipur, is probably one of the most known temples among the Śākadvīpiyas. It also includes an arena to watch sunrise during the festivals. The community promotes and finances the building up of new temples. The ancient Sun temple of Koṇārka (13th century), in Orissa, no longer active, was for sure a point of reference for the community and sun cult in general in ancient times.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.179 sqq.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The northern iconography of the Sun god is characterised by the union of Indian and Iranian elements, and it has probably been influenced by the foreign Śākadvīpiya Sun cult. In the Sām̐ba-purāṇa, Sām̐ba finds a statue of the Sun god in the Candrabhāgā river. The image is described in Sām̐ba-purāṇa 31: it has long eyes with thick eyelashes, and is smiling, with red-coloured lips like the Bimba fruit; it wears the avyaṅga (i.e. the Zoroastrian sacrificial girdle v. 18), a diadem/crown (v. 17b), and many other ornaments, like bracelets, bangles, a necklace, anklets and earrings. In both hands, he holds a lotus. The iconography of the Sun god is also described by Varāhamihira's Br̐hatsaṁhitā 58: the god should be dressed in northern style, and his dress should cover his body from breast to feet; he must wear armour. He should hold a lotus in both hands, and wear a diadem and the girdle around his waist; he must have earrings and a necklace. His face should be pleasant, with a smile. To confirm this iconography, a statue and relief found in Mathurā represent the Sun god wearing a long, heavy garment and boots, and holding a sword.

Reference: Kanchan Chakrabarti. Society, Religion and Art of the Kushāṇa India. Calcutta: K.P. Bagchi & Company.

Reference: Martina Palladino. Alcuni spunti di riflessione sui Maga Brāhmaṇa. p.171-175

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.86-88

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Sun god is depicted with Indian attributes, such as lotuses, a diadem, bracelets, but also Iranian, such as the sacrificial girdle, boots and a sword.
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
 - No
- ↳ Humans:
 - No
- ↳ Other features of iconography:
 - No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: The ground on which temples are built becomes a sacred space.

- ↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:
 - "Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...
 - No
 - Notes: Environmental features are not fundamental, but many sacred sites are built nearby water sources. In fact, water offering is one of the most important ritual practices.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - Optional (common)
 - Notes: Many Hindus go and visit places which are particularly significant for their tradition: for instance, many Śākadvīpiyas visit Koṅārka temple (13th century) in Orissa, probably the most important place for Sun cult in India.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The inner self, or ātman, is the part of the individual that is connected with the brahman, which can be defined as a kind of universal soul. The body is transitory and decaying.

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Notes: Like the other Hindus, the Śākadvīpīyas believe in rebirth and the continuous cycle of saṃsāra.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: The Hindus believe in rebirth based on life-transcending causality (karman). The range of rebirth goes from the lowest point of a blade of grass to the highest one of a divinity. The best rebirth is the male human being: in fact, it is the only form in which the man can free himself from the cycle of rebirth and reach liberation (mokṣa or mukti).

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: The Śākadvīpīyas, like the other Hindus, cremate corpses.

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The high god is the Sun god in his anthropomorphic form. In *Sāmba-purāṇa* 29, 2-3, it is stated that the sun had previously been worshipped as a disc, a *maṇḍala*; according to the legend, *Sāmba* finds a statue of the Sun god in his anthropomorphic form, built by the god *Viśvakarman* with the wood of the *kalpa* tree. Since the sun was generally represented as a disc or a wheel in ancient India, and even in Iran we do not find anthropomorphic representations of the sun, we may assume that this character came from the Greek influence and the assimilation of Greek, Iranian and then Indian divinities in Asia Minor and in the *Kuṣāna* cult.

Reference: Martina Palladino. *Alcuni spunti di riflessione sui Maga Brāhmaṇa*. p.171-175

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– Yes

Notes: According to the *Purāṇic* texts, the Sun god anciently generated the *Sākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas*, i.e. the religious elite. More precisely, according to *Bhaviṣya-purāṇa* 1, 117, 23b-24, they emerged from the Sun god's body while he was meditating.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: The high god is merciful and helpful with any of his devotees. However, the priests performing rituals have a special connection with the deities and the high god.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

Notes: Even if no direct mention of the god's goodness or badness can be found in the texts, we may assume that like any other Hindu god, even the Sun god is capable of atrocious punishments and misbehaviour towards human beings. Moreover, the sun as a natural element can burn or lead to drought. In the Hindu context, an ethic judgement of the god is not applicable, as the divinities possess many human behavioural features.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: He heals from sickness (in particular leprosy)

Notes: According to the Śākadvīpiya legend and Iranian and Indian beliefs, the Sun god can heal from sickness, and especially from leprosy. Sāmba, through his devotion to the Sun god, recovers health and his physical appearance.

Reference: Martina Palladino. *Alcuni spunti di riflessione sui Maga Brāhmaṇa*. p.161-165

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The high god has a total knowledge of the world and rules over it in his natural and divine forms.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– No

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: He is omniscient.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Throughout the Sāmba- and the Bhaviṣya-purāṇa passages, the Sun god is asked to grant boons and prosperity to the worshippers for their devotion. Even to Sāmba himself the Sun god grants healing from leprosy and glory.

Reference: V.C. Srivastava. *Sāmba-Purāṇa: With an Exhaustive Introduction, Sanskrit Text, English Translation, Notes & Index of Verses*. Delhi: Parimal Publications.

Reference: Martina Palladino. *The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present* (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna.

Reference: Heinrich von Stietencron. *Indische Sonnenpriester. Sāmba und die Śākadvīpiya-Brāhmaṇa: eine textkritische und religionsgeschichtliche Studie*

zum indischen Sonnenkult. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– No

Notes: The Sun god, like many other Hindu gods, punishes misbehaviours towards him. In particular, it is mentioned that the Sun god's feet cannot be represented in images, otherwise the artist would suffer from leprosy.

Reference: V.C. Srivastava. Sun-worship in Ancient India. Allahabad: Indological Publications. p.223

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Especially through his natural agency, he grows and destroys, heals or burns.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The Sun god exhibits compassion towards his worshippers and generosity towards them (Sāmba- and Bhaviṣya-purāṇa).

Reference: V.C. Srivastava. Sāmba-Purāṇa: With an Exhaustive Introduction, Sanskrit Text, English Translation, Notes & Index of Verses. Delhi: Parimal Publications.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna.

Reference: Heinrich von Stietencron. Indische Sonnenpriester. Sāmba und die Śākadvīpiya-Brāhmaṇa: eine textkritische und religionsgeschichtliche Studie zum indischen Sonnenkult. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The Sun god can be irate with human beings or other deities.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The pūjā practice, common to any Hindu trend and towards any god, consists in taking care of the god's idol, feed him, wash him and dress him. The god, in the form of the idol, possesses all the human needs.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas are Hindus, and therefore worship the complete Hindu pantheon. Moreover, nowadays Śākadvīpiya priests are considered experts not only in the Sun cult, but in the pūjā of the other gods as well.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.134

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: He is worshipped with many names and in many forms.

Notes: The Sun god is worshipped with twenty-one different names (Sāmba-purāṇa 25, 2-7 / Bhaviṣya-purāṇa 1, 128, 2-7) and venerated in twelve different forms (Sāmba-purāṇa 4, 6-20 / Bhaviṣya-purāṇa 1, 74, 7-22). Among them, he is also identified with Mihira, the Middle Persian form of the name Miθra/Mitra, the Indo-Iranian god.

Reference: Martina Palladino. Alcuni spunti di riflessione sui Maga Brāhmaṇa. p.171-175

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Hindu gods can appear to humans in waking. Moreover, the sun and sun light are also part of the everyday natural environment.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: According to Sāmba-purāṇa (24-25) and Bhaviṣya-purāṇa (1, 127-128) the Sun god speaks to Sāmba through multiple visions in his sleep.

Reference: V.C. Srivastava. Sāmba-Purāṇa: With an Exhaustive Introduction, Sanskrit Text, English Translation, Notes & Index of Verses. Delhi: Parimal Publications.

Reference: Heinrich von Stietencron. Indische Sonnenpriester. Sāmba und die Sākadvīpiya-Brāhmana: eine textkritische und religionsgeschichtliche Studie zum indischen Sonnenkult. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The priests perform rituals to reach out the gods and grant prosperity, but the relationship with the divinities is not exclusively established through them.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The god's idol.

Notes: The god's idol represents the god's presence on earth. According to the Sākadvīpiya legend, Sāmba finds a statue of the Sun god on the shore of the Candrabhāgā river, builds up a temple and installs the idol there (throughout the Sāmba- and the Bhaviṣya-purāṇa; even Varāha-purāṇa 177 and Varāhamihira's Bṛhatsamhitā 58 refer to the installation of the sun's image.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Sākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.86 sqq. in particular

Reference: V.C. Srivastava. Sāmba-Purāṇa: With an Exhaustive Introduction, Sanskrit Text, English Translation, Notes & Index of Verses. Delhi: Parimal Publications.

Reference: Heinrich von Stietencron. Indische Sonnenpriester. Sāmba und die Sākadvīpiya-Brāhmana: eine textkritische und religionsgeschichtliche Studie zum indischen Sonnenkult. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: Due to the continuous cycle of rebirth, people do not remain on earth as spirits.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Many non-human supernatural beings are present in the Hindu pantheon, like mythological animals (for instance, the gods' vehicles, such as Viṣṇu's serpent Śeṣa, Śiva's bull Nandi or Gaṇeśa's mouse) or anthropomorphic animals like Gaṇeśa (man with an elephant's head) or Hanumat (an anthropomorphic monkey). Then, we find demons and other supernatural entities. In particular, the Sun god has the divine seven horses of his chariot.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: All the supernatural beings are in strict contact with the gods or the supernatural spheres and they are generally omniscient or have anyway an extensive knowledge of the human world and its vicissitudes.

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
– No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
– No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
– No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
Notes: All the supernatural beings can interfere with human affairs, directly or indirectly, and have agency on the terrestrial sphere. They can reward the devotees and punish misbehaviours of men.
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
Notes: Any supernatural being can affect the world and the life of men even indirectly, since they can walk on earth and have relationships with human beings.
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes
Notes: Every supernatural being can be merciful and helpful towards human beings or other entities.
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings can be jealous, disrespectful or cruel towards human beings or other entities.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Their images are nourished and looked after as any other god's idol.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Human behavioural features.

Notes: In general, even non-human supernatural beings possess many human behavioural features according to the context or as dominant feature of their character.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: Even if there are no mixed human-divine beings, some human beings, like the heroes of the Mahābhārata epic or Manu, the first man, are anyway different from the common human beings and possess almost divine features.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The Hindu pantheon and mythology includes a very high number of different supernatural beings, abiding the earth, the god's worlds and the sky.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: Not all Hindu gods belong to the same family, but some of them have relationships. The Sun god himself has two wives, Nikṣubhā and Rājñī (see for instance Sāmba-purāṇa 84, 13).

Reference: V.C. Srivastava. Sāmba-Purāṇa: With an Exhaustive Introduction, Sanskrit Text, English Translation, Notes & Index of Verses. Delhi: Parimal Publications.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna.

Reference: Heinrich von Stietencron. Indische Sonnenpriester. Sāmba und die Śākadvīpiya-Brāhmaṇa: eine textkritische und religionsgeschichtliche Studie zum indischen Sonnenkult. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

Notes: Even if the Hindu pantheon has not a real hierarchy, every branch of cult or even each devotee establish a sort of personal hierarchy of the gods, deserving a higher place to some divinities.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Each god or supernatural being has a particular function and is associated with a specific domain. The Sun god represents his natural element and reflects many of its properties (he is shining, he drives a chariot with horses in the sky, etc.).

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The gods' presence in the human world determines an indirect monitoring, even if a real monitoring on the human beings' behaviour is not present. People have to behave and respect a social system made of caste rules; but the gods do not really interfere with it, since they are part of the saṃsāra (cycle of rebirth), too. However, people must not misbehave in rituals and in everyday life not to offend the gods and attract their anger and punishment.

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural monitoring is especially focused on prosocial norm, not from an ethical or moral point of view, but to maintain social order based on each individual's social status and profession.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

 - ↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Some kinds of food, such as cow meat, are strictly prohibited in Hinduism, and especially for the sacerdotal class, the Brahmins.
 - ↳ Sacred space(s):

– No

Notes: Sacred spaces are open to Hindu devotees and also to other religions' adherents.
 - ↳ Sacred object(s):

– No

Notes: There is no real taboo or prohibition on the objects themselves, but rather on preserving their purity by not letting other people touch them.
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The correctness of the ritual and the pūjā.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: According to the Manusmṛti, a treatise on social law, the murder of a coreligionist is punished on the basis of the victim's social status: the murder of a Brahmin is the highest crime, but the death of a low caste person, especially if provoked by a higher caste one, is not punished severely. The murdered is judged by men, but also by the gods according to the same principles.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Notes: In Hinduism, sex is not a taboo and the gods themselves experience different kinds of physical intercourse.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: The gods care about misbehaviour only if the offence and the lie harm or annoy them.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Oaths are generally part of the social and political position of the individual, and therefore, the gods appreciate them to be respected and honoured.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

Notes: The gods do not care about general laziness, but do care about laziness in fulfilling one's social and political duties according to his/her status.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - No
 - Notes: A part of the sacred scriptures, the Vedas, is focused on spells, magic and divination. The Śākadvipīyas are particularly versed in astrology, which can be seen as an art belonging to the sphere of sorcery.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
 - Notes: If shirking risk affects the expected social and political behaviour of the individual, the gods may not be pleased.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Disrespect in general is not considered a proper behaviour, especially if it comes from the members of the highest castes.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Crimes create problems in the society and therefore the gods are generally not pleased with them. Curiously, in Hinduism even crimes are regulated by laws: thieves must steal other people's properties according to the dharma of the thief (see for instance the work Dharmacauryarasāyana 'the elixir of theft according to dharma').
 - Reference: Alessandro Passi. L'elisir del furto secondo il dharma (Dharmacauryarasayana). Milano: Adelphi.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Ritual observance and pūjā are the most important practices to worship and honour the gods.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Rituals must be performed by the priests in the correct way. The incorrect performance of a ritual practice is very dangerous for the performer and for the person who benefits from the ritual because it can irritate the gods and lead to punishments.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No
 - Notes: The affiliation to Hinduism is by birth and not by conversion.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Yes
 - Notes: According to some treatises focused on physical pleasure and sensual life, such as Kāmasūtra, personal hygiene is an important step to pursue the goal of kāma, the sensual pleasure, and please the gods.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: In the Śākadvipīya mythology, the god Kṛṣṇa curses his own son Sāmba with leprosy because his attractive appearance is distracting Kṛṣṇa's women.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvipīya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their

History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna.

Reference: V.C. Srivastava. *Sāmba-Purāṇa: With an Exhaustive Introduction, Sanskrit Text, English Translation, Notes & Index of Verses*. Delhi: Parimal Publications.

Reference: Heinrich von Stietencron. *Indische Sonnenpriester. Sāmba und die Sākadvīpiya-Brāhmana: eine textkritische und religionsgeschichtliche Studie zum indischen Sonnenkult*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: In Hindu mythology, the agent of the punishment is generally known because it is linked to a specific domain or the reason of it is known as well.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The misbehaviour towards a god can affect the rebirth and grant a lower status in the next life. However, this is the result of the human action and the karman rule, not the effect of a direct punishment by someone else. Therefore, the agent of the punishment is the man himself.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Any entity can curse or punish other entities.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Generally the punishment is the result of a voluntary or accidental offence towards the gods. The reason of the punishment is generally known by the offender, either before deliberately committing the offence or after the punishment, if the offence was accidental.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Notes: The supernatural being are not involved in punishments pertaining the social sphere. For this environment, strict caste and social rules have been put in place since ancient times.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: The reason may not be known to the recipient, but there is always one behind the punishment.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Done because of an offence towards the gods.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Atrocious punishments can be meted out according to personal and social status. For instance, a king or a warrior can be defeated in battle, a farmer can experience famine and

drought, any person can have health issues or have no descendants. Moreover, the curse or punishment can be passed to the lineage.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

Notes: The punishment with leprosy is the starting point of the Śākadvīpiya mythology.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: The Hindu gods are particularly generous with the devotees who worship them in the correct way. They grant prosperity, richness, health, progeny and victory. The Sun god grants multiform boons to his worshippers. The rewards are described throughout the passages of the Sāmba- and Bhaviṣya-purāṇa. Sāmba gets his recovery from leprosy and his beautiful appearance back thanks to his devotion to the Sun god.

Reference: V.C. Srivastava. Sāmba-Purāṇa: With an Exhaustive Introduction, Sanskrit Text, English Translation, Notes & Index of Verses. Delhi: Parimal Publications.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna.

Reference: Heinrich von Stietenron. Indische Sonnenpriester. Sāmba und die Śākadvīpiya-Brāhmaṇa: eine textkritische und religionsgeschichtliche Studie zum indischen Sonnenkult. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Any supernatural being can grant boons and rewards.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The karmic retribution is based on human beings' actions, and therefore the reward of a better birth is granted by the individual himself by acting in the appropriate manner.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Appropriate ritual performances and devotion particularly please the gods, who reward the devotees.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness!:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: The cause of the reward may not be known to the recipient, but a reason always lies behind it.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Boons and rewards are bestowed according to the personal and social status of the recipient. They generally consist in luck, prosperity, health and power for the devotee and his lineage.

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Rewards are pleasant, but the main goal remains the liberation by breaking the cycle of rebirth.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Notes: Hinduism and Śākadvīpiyas do not condemn sensory pleasure and it undoubtedly represent a form of reward. However, everything must be done according to social and religious rules, and this therefore excludes extreme pleasures.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Hinduism is a highly normative religion. As a matter of fact, Hinduism is a way of life based on religious-social norms, which permeate every aspect of a Hindu person's existence. Caste system, purity laws, social hierarchy are only the basis of a system that tries to target and regulate any aspect of life.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Morality is not a feature of Hinduism. Every action has to conform to one's personal and social status, and has to be in agreement with the religious and social law (dharma).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Śākadvīpiyas are Brahmins, and therefore, since they belong to the highest social class, they have to incarnate the highest values. In fact, they must be an example for the other castes to grant social order and appropriate behaviour.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: According to the mythological account of late text Sāmavajaya, the Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas, after having worshipped the Sun god and having healed Sām̐ba, want to return to their land (Iran). While they are going, they hear the lamentation of the prince of Magadha, Suloman, who is about to kill himself because he has contracted leprosy. The Śākadvīpiyas, touched, decide to help him, and in reward, they receive some lands and decide to permanently settle there.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of

Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna.

Reference: Albrecht Weber. Über zwei Parteischriften zu Gunsten der Maga, resp. Çâkadvîpiya Brâhmaṇa. p.

- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - No
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Purity is probably the most important feature of the Brahmanical conduct.
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Family affiliation and obedience are fundamental points of the Brahmanical behaviour.
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The cooperation is generally restricted to the Brahmanical group itself.
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - No
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Brahmins are expected to be the leaders of the society.
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The status is very important and distinctive for the Brahmanical class.
- ↳ Humility / modesty:

- No
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - No
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Brahmin represents the ancient sacerdotal caste and devotion is one of their highest qualities.
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Marriage is a fundamental stage in the life of a Hindu man, including priests. The Śākadvīpīyas are an endogamic group and marriages are arranged according to the Hindu system of puras (principalities or cities) and gotras (lineage).

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpīya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.128 sqq.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: According to Hindu scriptures (and images carved on temples), sexual constraint is not registered: any kind of sexual intercourse, including homosexual, adulterous, orgiastic, etc. seems to be permitted. In fact, human physical love reflects the gods' sexual life and is regulated by specific treatises such as the Kāmasūtra.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: The Śākadvīpīyas have specific fasting in honour of the Sun god. The most important one is called Ratha Saptamī Vrata and it is described in the Bhaviṣya-purāṇa 1, 50.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpīya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.170

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Some foods are forbidden, like cow meat, and most Brahmins are totally vegetarian. Many Śākadvīpīyas also avoid tamasic nocive food such as garlic, onions or white sugar.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The pūjā to the gods has to be performed every day and the Śākadvīpīyas must visit the temples.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: The Śākadvīpīya Brāhmaṇas are even marginalized by the other Brahmin groups with the accusation of not being real Brahmins. In the Purāṇic texts, they defend themselves against the accusation of being devalakas priests (Bhaviṣya-purāṇa 1, 117, 5; 139, 18, 21-22), who attend the deity's service, and because of this activity, they are considered impure. Moreover, in Bhaviṣya-purāṇa 1, 126, 1 sqq., we find the curious claim that their food is edible and not impure. Unfortunately, we do not have enough information to reconstruct the social environment in which this section was composed, but we may postulate that at a certain moment, the Śākadvīpīyas lost their status of brāhmaṇas to such an extent that their food was considered inedible.

Reference: Helmut Humbach. Iranische Sonnenpriester in Indien. Zeitschrift der Deutschen Morgenländischen Gesellschaft. Supplementa, 1(3)

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpīya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.99 in particular

Reference: Heinrich von Stietencron. Indische Sonnenpriester. Sāmba und die Śākadvipīya-Brāhmaṇa: eine textkritische und religionsgeschichtliche Studie zum indischen Sonnenkult. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

— Yes

Notes: Private cult and house rituals are very important for the Hindus and represent the daily service to the divinity.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

— Hours: 12

Notes: The Śākadvipīyas generally perform the daily pūjā (adoration) in the morning like any other Hindu group. However, being Sun worshippers, many of them reported a double pūjā for the sun at sunrise and sunset.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvipīya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.170 sqq.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

— Yes

Notes: Temple gatherings are very important for the Śākadvipīyas as for the Hindus in general.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

— Number of participants: 300

Notes: The Śākadvipīyas also attend general Hindu temple gatherings and festivities. The specific Śākadvipīya festivals, namely Sūrya (or Ratha) Saptamī and Chhath, gather only the members of the community, and therefore the numbers are lower.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

— Average interval [hours]: 168

Notes: There is no fixed day or time to go to the temple. Many Hindus go to the temple once per week, but during festivities, which may last even several days, the followers go to the temple everyday. The Śākadvipīya Brāhmaṇas attend the temple for pūjā as any other Hindu group.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

— Yes

Notes: Orthodoxy checks are granted by Paṇḍits, who provide the exegesis of the sacred texts such as the Vedas. The interpretation of the scriptures is not univocal even among the group of the Śākadvipīyas, and each small group of adherents has its own reading of the texts.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

— Yes

Notes: Priests look after the temples and are the knowers of the correct ritual practices. Recitation and performance are codified and transmitted from generation to generation.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

— Yes

Notes: The Hindu pūjā and celebrations do not imply the synchronic recitation of passages. However, we find sung prayers, synchronic gestures and more priests reciting together.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

— No

Notes: The ritual soma beverage, very important in the Indo-Iranian ritual, is an intoxicating drink which was used in solemn rituals. Nowadays, there is generally no consumption of intoxicants during the rituals.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas are a subgroup belonging to a caste of the Hindu society.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Probably there are state famine relief plans available to the Śākadvīpiyas as well.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: Even if a real poverty relief plan is not institutionalized, the members donate some offerings to the temple and the community to help each other.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They can benefit from state assistance if needed.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are state and private institutions for the care for the elderly and infirm.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: State and private schools are open to the Śākadvīpiyas.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with state institutional bureaucracy.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Public food storage is provided by state or private institutions.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Water management is provided by state or private institutions.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Transportation infrastructure is provided by state or private institutions.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Taxes are levied by the Indian state.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: If needed, the group's adherents interact with the state police force.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: If needed, the group's adherents interact with state judicial system.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by the state law.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:
– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:
– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are subjected to the Constitution of India and the state legal system.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: If needed, the Indian military force protects the Śākadvīpiya population as well.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: For both religious and social matters, the Śākadvīpiya communities use nowadays their own modern languages. The ancient texts are in Sanskrit, which is a language used by many religious groups, but also for poetry and different kind of literature.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The ancient calendar contained in the text Pañcasiddhāntikā (I, 23-25) by the astronomer and astrologer Varāhamira (6th century CE), probably a Śākadvīpiya himself, is peculiar and shows many common features with the Zoroastrian one. The contemporary communities are still aware of this author and his work.

Reference: Antonio Panaino. The Year of the Maga Brāhmaṇas.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Nowadays, the Śākadvīpiya group does not follow a different calendar, but the official Indian one, as they have mainly been absorbed by Hindu cult and customs.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

— No

Notes: According to Bhaviṣya-purāṇa 1, 147, 4, Śākadvīpiyas cannot be involved in trade or agriculture. Therefore, they do not cultivate, produce or sell their own food. Nowadays, however, some of them are involved in trade, but generally not connected to food.

Reference: Martina Palladino. The Sun-Worshipping Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas. An Analysis of Their History and Customs from Ancient Times to the Present (PhD Thesis). University of Bologna. p.98 sqq.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: They buy food provided by the government or private producers.

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

— Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Śākadvīpiya Brāhmaṇas buy their food in the same shops the other Indians do their own shopping. Most of them are vegetarian, so they do not consume meat or fish.

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